

**EFFECT OF THE DITERPENOID ALKALOID KARAKOLINE
AND THEIR DERIVATIVE 14-O-BENZOILKARAKOLINE OF RAT
AORTIC SMOOTH MUSCLE CELLS**

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Diterpenoid alkaloids are compounds found in plants that have been studied for their potential therapeutic effects. One such compound is karakoline, which has been shown to exhibit relaxant activity in various systems. Studies have found that karakoline can exert relaxant effects on smooth muscle, including in the gastrointestinal tract, respiratory system, and blood vessels. This may be due to its ability to interact with certain receptors or ion channels involved in muscle relaxation [1].

Experimental setup, specimen preparation: Thoracic aortas were isolated from white rats (200-250g) and cleaned of adventitia. The aortas were then cut into ring segments (3-4 mm in length). Tissue bath setup: The aortic rings were mounted on stainless steel hooks and suspended in a 5-ml jacketed tissue bath filled with Krebs' physiological salt solution, which was aerated with a gas mixture of 95% O₂ and 5% CO₂ to maintain optimal conditions for the tissue. Measuring Contractile Activity: The contractile responses of the aortic rings were recorded under isometric conditions using a Grass FT03 force-displacement transducer connected to a chart recorder (Endim621.02). This setup allowed for the measurement of the force generated during muscle contractions. Induction of Contractions: The aortic rings were stimulated to contract using high KCl or norepinephrine, which are known to induce contractions in smooth muscle [2].

Results and discussion. In preliminary experiments karakoline and 14-O-benzoilkarakoline in wide range of concentration had no effect on basal tone of aortic preparation, but at concentration-dependent manner relax preparations pre-contracted by 1 μM PE. In these conditions karakoline start the relaxation

only at a concentration of 50 μ M and produce maximum of relaxation of 24,2 $\pm$ 4,1 % at a 200 μ M. In contrast, the relaxant effects of 14-O-benzoilkarakoline first occurred at 1 μ M and maximum of relaxation of 80,2 $\pm$ 4,2 % achieved at a 100 μ M. These effects of alkaloids on contraction induced by high PE, mediated by activation of L-type receptor-operated Ca²⁺ channels, could be attributed to inhibition of extracellular Ca²⁺ entry. However, karakoline and 14-O-benzoilkarakoline with similar efficiency and potencies produced relaxation of aortic preparation pre-contracted by norepinephrine. These results suggest that studied alkaloids relaxed the rat aorta by suppressing the Ca²⁺ entry into smooth muscle cells through both voltage- and receptor-operated calcium channels. The more potent relaxant activity of 14-O-benzoilkarakoline apparently is due to presence in his structure of benzoyl group at carbon atom C1 nstead of hydroxyl group of karakoline.

Conclusion:The study provides valuable insights into the pharmacological properties of karakoline and its derivative, potentially paving the way for the development of new therapeutic agents for muscle relaxation. Further research would be needed to elucidate the exact mechanisms of action, optimal dosages, and potential side effects of these alkaloids in various physiological systems.

References:

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